

Interview Guide for the Requirements Analysis for an Application Profile/Metadata Schema for Energy Research Software

Introduction to the Interview Situation

The interview should be recorded if possible, ideally with a voice recorder or as a recording of the computer audio during video conferences. This technique should be tested beforehand.

If the interviewee does not agree to the recording, notes and keywords to the questions should be noted down.

A business card, if the interviews take place in person, always looks good. This should be given to the interviewee for questions.

As a general rule, avoid yes/no questions in the interview situation, as these disrupt the flow of the conversation. Give examples only if the open-ended questions do not lead to answers.

Goal (as a Reminder)

The application profile provides the basis for the registry for energy research software. It should contain all relevant categories for the software. These are both domain specific (What exactly is the software for?) and cross-domain (What is the quality and scope of the software?).

Important: It is not about how the software should be, but what information about the software should be captured!

Metadata for Energy Research Software – Interview Guide

1. Introduction (approx. 5-10 min).

Indication of confidentiality and voluntary nature of the answers, question about recording.

Here the interviewee should be asked again whether the interview may be recorded; if this is answered in the affirmative, the recording can now be turned on.

Short self-introduction, interview as part of my dissertation project:

1. The goal is to develop a database in which software artifacts from energy research are cataloged (cf. library catalog).

2. Introductory Questions (ca. 10-15 min)

About the interviewee: questions about professional background, own professional and experience background.

The following questions should be asked throughout, they serve to loosen up the conversation and should show first hints and thoughts of the participant in order to give a thematic introduction to the interview situation. It is important that it should kept brief.

1. Which aspects of energy system do you focus on in your research?
2. What do you use research software for?
3. How much of the software is developed for industrial purposes?
4. What kind of software do you write yourself?
5. What kind of software from third parties do you usually use?
6. How do you use software from others? To what extent do you make modifications to it yourself?
7. Which overview papers about research software in your field do you know?

3. Main Part (Query of the Different FAIR Criteria).

- *Please imagine that there is already a registry containing all the important software artifacts ever developed for energy research, a library catalog for energy research software*

- Structured according to
 - Findability - Search
 - Findability - Selection
 - Accessibility
 - Interoperability
 - Reusability

3.1 Findability - Search (ca. 15-20)

Initially, the focus should be on finding suitable research software.

Experience with search

1. How have you searched for software so far?
 - a) What platforms have you used to search?
 - b) What did you like about these platforms?
 - c) What did you dislike about them?
 - d) How often do you search for new software?

What are you looking for?

2. What kind of software do you usually look for?
 - a) E.g. scripts, complete models as libraries, smaller software snippets, executable programs, frameworks, models, post/preprocessing software, etc.
3. For what use cases are you looking for software?
 - a) E.g. for direct simulation or for building simulations.

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Properties when searching

4. What features of the software are important to you?
 - a) E.g. scope, covered functionalities energy system etc.
5. What information do you need about the covered functionalities in the energy system?

Concrete thematic characteristics (if not already mentioned)

6. Which properties regarding the mapped energy systems are relevant for you?
 - a) Temporal, spatial resolution, etc.?
7. How detailed do you need information about how the software works?
8. How relevant is it for you what is not possible with the software?

Concrete technical features (if not already mentioned)

9. Which features are relevant for you regarding optimization?
 - a) E.g. optimizers used, functionalities covered
10. To what extent is it relevant for you if the software has a GUI?
11. To what extent is performance of the software relevant for you?
 - a) What information is relevant for you regarding computational effort (time, resources)? How accurate does this information need to be?
 - i. E.g. computing time, required RAM, CPU etc.
12. To what extent does it make a difference to you whether you only have to install the software or need a framework (such as python) to run it?
13. How relevant is the type of operating system required for you?

3.2 Findability - Selection (approx. 15-20)

Now imagine that you have found different software. We now focus on the selection process and the necessary information.

Features in the selection process

1. Which characteristics are important to you for the selection of software?
 - a. E.g. speed, programming language
2. To what extent is it important to you whether the software is open source?
 - a. What role does the exact license play in deciding whether to use it?
3. By what characteristics would you judge the quality of the software?
 - a. E.g.: previous use, scope, review, programming language, size of development team, etc.

Concrete quality characteristics (if not already mentioned)

4. To what extent is it important to you whether and how software is documented?
 - a. E.g. README, readthedocs, examples
5. To what extent is it relevant for you how extensively the software has been tested or that tests exist?
6. How important is it for you if the software has already been validated against other software?

Concrete general characteristics (if not already mentioned)

7. How relevant is it for you, from whom the software comes, from which person or from which institution?
8. How relevant is it for you with which financial means the software was developed?
9. Which information are you interested in concerning the community of the software?
10. To what extent is it relevant for you whether and which scientific publications or projects have been developed in the context of the development or use of the software?

3.3 Accessibility (approx. 5-10)

Now we focus on accessibility - what is needed to download the research software.

1. Which platforms are trustworthy from your point of view to download software?
 - a. E.g. gitlab, github, university websites etc.
2. How important is it for you that the software is in a version control system?
3. How important is it for you that the release date of the software you download is clearly visible?
4. To what extent do you check downloaded content?
 - a. E.g. by means of hashcodes

3.4 Interoperability (ca. 5-10)

The next point is interoperability - what does the software need to do to work with other data that is currently in use?

1. To what extent are standardized interfaces relevant for you to use software with your own data?
2. Which standardized interfaces do you know?
3. Which standardized interfaces do you use?
4. How detailed do you think the interfaces of your software have to be defined? (down to variable level or more abstract?)
5. To what extent is it relevant for you, with which other software the software is compatible?
6. To what extent is it relevant for you, with which existing open data sets the software is directly compatible?
7. How important is it for you which solver was used and if it is exchangeable?

3.5 Reusability (ca. 5-10)

The last step is reusability - what knowledge is needed about the software to use it concretely for own research projects.

Developing software

1. Which aspects of software are important to you in order to decide whether you want to continue your own developments based on the software?

Own use of software

Let us now return to your use of software:

2. What is the practice for sharing source code in your institute?
3. How does the practice of publishing source code look like in your institute?

4. Final Questions and Farewell (approx. 10)

1. What additional information do you think should be collected about energy research software?
2. What additional difficulties do you see in developing such a database?
3. Which colleagues do you know who are also working with research software in the energy research? Can you recommend other people to talk to?

If you think of anything else after our conversation, please feel free to contact me.

The voice recorder can be stopped here.

Thank you for the opportunity and for participating in the interview and supporting the research project!